

Privacy Concerns of Contact Tracing Apps: An Analysis with the APCO Model

Daniel Neumann
2065824

Marco Haalboom
2064602

Floris Langver
2058743

Luc van der Geest
2062364

ABSTRACT

With the increasing number of COVID-19 infections, the Dutch and German governments reacted by implementing contact tracing apps. Although the privacy of citizens using tracing apps is guaranteed by technological solutions, previous research indicates privacy concerns among citizens. The predicting factors for privacy concerns have so far been determined in the context of e-commerce and social networking. The new context of a pandemic and governments being in the role of tracing app-providers lead to a need for new research. This research introduces a modified APCO model with trust in government as a new predictor to identify the factors influencing privacy concerns. After conducting a standardized survey with 64 participants, it is shown that computer anxiety and trust in government influence privacy concerns regarding the contact tracing app. Furthermore, higher privacy concerns have a negative effect on the intention to accept the privacy of the contact tracing app.

Keywords

COVID-19, Contact Tracing Apps, Privacy Concerns, APCO Model, Government

INTRODUCTION

When the COVID-19 pandemic spread across the world in the year 2020, citizens and governments faced new challenges and adopted different measures to minimize the impact of the pandemic. One measure was the development and implementation of a contact tracing app (CTA). States had their own CTA developed as part of the confrontation with COVID-19 (European Union, 2020).

A CTA enables automatic tracking of the contacts and is only effective in the containment of the pandemic if at least 60% of the population of a country have installed as well as activated the CTA on their smartphone (Hinch, 2020). However, in the Netherlands, only 22.5% use the government's CTA

(Rijksoverheid, 2020), in Germany 26,9% (Medicus, 2020). Therefore, governments are trying various measures to increase the use (Rijksoverheid, 2020; Deutscher Ärzteverlag GmbH, 2020).

Accordingly, at the beginning of the implementation of the CTA, research focused on adoption by using the Technology Acceptance Model. It showed that privacy concerns have among other factors a negative impact on the adoption of CTA (Walrave, Waeterloos, & Ponnet, 2020).

This is worth mentioning, as the CTAs in Germany and Netherlands were developed on the principle of privacy by design and data minimization. The compliance with privacy laws was implemented through technologies such as Bluetooth and encryption, so that both citizens and governments cannot identify and trace citizens via the app (CoronaMelder, 2020; Medicus, 2020). While some non-European governments were given full access to personal data with the app and the usage of the app was made mandatory, the mainly ethical, legal and privacy-related concerns of European experts were taken into account and realized (Trang, Trenz, Weiger, & Cheung, 2020).

The remarkable attention for protecting citizens' privacy in the development of the CTA by the German and Dutch governments is in marked contrast to the privacy concerns. Accordingly, this research aims to identify the factors that explain the fact that a tracing app that does not allow identification of the individual user at all, is still considered with high concerns and little trust of citizens in privacy-related aspects. The findings could help understanding to address privacy concerns in a coordinated way in order to achieve the necessary 60% population share of CTA users.

Problem Statement

Privacy concerns in relation to CTAs developed by governments are an unresearched issue. Previous research on CTA has a focus on technology adoption. That considers privacy concerns only as part of the problem of lack of acceptance of CTAs.

The antecedents of privacy concerns remain unanswered (Walrave et al., 2020).

The APCO model has the construct privacy concerns at the center and compares antecedents and outcomes in relation to privacy concerns. The antecedents represent the independent variables on the privacy concerns while the outcome is the acceptance of the privacy. The APCO model and other privacy concern models have been continuously researched and developed in the context of e-commerce and social networking in recent years (Degirmenci, 2020).

However, based on the new context, this understanding does not seem to explain the privacy concerns of the CTA for the following three reasons. Firstly, the provider of the app is the respective government (European Union, 2020). Secondly, the goal of downloading a tracing is not based on the same reasons as e-commerce or social networking apps (Walrave et al., 2020). Lastly, there is a worldwide crisis situation due to the pandemic (WHO, 2020). It can be concluded that personal and situational factors of individuals changed due to the government safety measures. Such contextual factors are proven to be important in the understanding of information privacy concerns and could create a new insight and understanding in the matter (Bansal, Zahedi, & Gefen, 2008).

Research Question

All research questions refer to the Netherlands and Germany. The following question arises. Which factors are leading to an increased privacy concern of citizens regarding the CTA and to what extent do privacy concerns relate to the intention to accept the privacy of a CTA? To answer this, the following subdivision into theoretical and practical sub-questions is provided.

Theoretical sub-questions:

1. What are CTAs?
2. What is the relation of CTA to privacy?
3. What is privacy?
4. What are privacy concerns?
5. What is trust in government?
6. What is the APCO model?
7. What is the Information Boundary Theory?

Practical sub-questions:

1. To what extent does education level influence the privacy concerns towards CTAs?
2. To what extent do personal and situational differences such as prior privacy experience, privacy awareness and computer anxiety

influence the privacy concerns of CTAs?

3. To what extent does trust in government influence the privacy concerns of CTAs?
4. To what extent do privacy concerns regarding the CTAs influence the intention to accept the privacy of CTAs?

Relevance

The findings could be of relevance to governments, companies and institutions involved in the development and implementation of CTAs by providing insight into relevant antecedents of privacy concerns.

Less than a third of both the Dutch and German population has installed their respective CTA (Rijksoverheid, 2020; Centraal Bureau Statistiek, 2020; Medicus, 2020). Governments use measures to increase the number of active users by making commercials and creating awareness on how the app operates, as the effectivity of the CTAs depends on the level of adoption (Roorda, 2020; Deutscher Ärzteverband GmbH, 2020; Hinch, 2020). The findings could help to contribute to increase the adoption rate, providing insights into privacy concerns of citizens. Moreover, governments could gain a better understanding of the privacy related aspects of E-government solutions. E-government is a digital government which uses information technology to transfer data and supports communication to citizens (Joseph, 2013).

THEORY

Contact Tracing Apps

A CTA is a mobile application developed by governments to automate contact tracing. Mobile devices interact with each other with the Dutch and German CTA. Both recognize, with a Bluetooth connection, whether the person with the app has been close to someone who also has the app. Being closer to someone with the app leads to a stronger signal of Bluetooth. This way the app calculates an estimated distance between two persons (Brecht, 2020; Rijksoverheid, 2020). From a technological view the German and Dutch CTA are operating in a similar way. Physical proximity leads automatically to exchange encrypted codes through Bluetooth. This collection of data is done by an Exposure Notification System. It is then broadcasted through Rolling Proximity Identifiers (RPI) which are based on crypto-technology and are valid for 10-20 minutes. After this timeframe it will create new ones (Robert-Koch-Institut, 2020). Through this system the app can notify its users if they have been too close to a COVID-19 infected person (Basu, 2020). Governments' CTAs

can vary. In several countries the CTA is mandatory to download, for instance in India. In the Netherlands and Germany, the app is not mandatory (Basu, 2020).

Privacy

Defining the concept of privacy has received a substantive amount of scientific attention across diverse fields such as, philosophy, psychology, law, information systems and economics. However, in this pursuit, no single definition of privacy is defined that is accepted across all disciplines and acknowledged by all researchers. Two primary types of privacy can be defined, information privacy and physical privacy. This paper focusses solely on information privacy as this concerns the spread and gathering of personal information, as opposed to physical access to an individual's private space (Smith, Dinev, & Xu Heng, 2011). There are privacy laws in Europe, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the e-Privacy Directive. These laws are an exemplification of the increasing importance of information privacy among diverse countries (Bock, et al., 2020).

MUIPC Construct

Research in the social sciences uses privacy related proxy to measure privacy. As it can be challenging to accurately measure privacy itself, moreover, privacy depends on cognition and perception more so than it does on rational assessment (Smith et al., 2011). Within information systems research the primary proxy for privacy is the construct, privacy concerns. Privacy concern can be described as individuals being concerned about someone or something invading their privacy (Sheehan & Hoy, 2000). It can be operationalized through the scale of concern for information privacy (CFIP) (Smith, Milberg, & Burke, 1996). Since its introduction it has been the most widespread measure for an individual's privacy concerns (Smith et al., 2011). As information systems evolved over time, so did the measure for privacy concerns. Malhotra et al. (2004) introduced the scale of Internet Users' information privacy concerns (IUIPC) which adapted the CFIP into the internet context. More recently Xu, Gupta, Rosen and Carroll (2012) introduced the mobile users' information privacy concerns (MUIPC) which brought the IUIPC into the mobile context. It must be noted that these scales measure privacy concerns at the individual level. The MUIPC consists out of three subscales: perceived surveillance, perceived intrusion, and secondary use of personal information (Xu et al., 2012). Perceived surveillance refers to the monitoring of someone's activities through a mobile device (Xu et al., 2012). Mobile devices are equipped with sensors that can monitor a user's environment, movement, orientation, and location,

which in the first place enhances the user experience. However, this can also provoke privacy risks (Keith, Babb, Lowrey, Furner, & Abdullat, 2015). Perceived intrusion refers to the invasion or incursions into a person's life, for example, unnecessary location access requests by mobile apps can lead to such intrusions (Degirmenci, 2020). The third subscale concerns secondary use of personal information, which was also included in the CFIP scale (Smith et al., 1996). It is defined as the act of using collected personal information for other useful purposes than for which the data was collected, moreover, sharing this data with other parties that may find use in the collected data (Smith et al., 1996; Pee, 2011). As this study focusses on CTAs for mobile devices the MUIPC is selected to measure the construct privacy concerns, because of its proven accuracy in the mobile environment (Xu et al., 2012; Degirmenci, 2020).

Trust in Government

Trust can be generally defined as a state of being in which a person has the intention to take a vulnerable position based on a positive expectation of behavior or intention of someone else. This definition can generally also be applied to government. However, as a government is a complex organization substantiated judgement of a citizen on a governments' competence, good intentions and truthfulness is challenging (Cullen & Reilly, 2008). In order to measure this construct, in the 1950's the US government created the SRC/CPS National Election Survey to monitor citizens trust in government. Over time the measures used in the SRC/CPS survey have shown deficiencies in their accuracy. Therefore, this research uses a revised version designed by Craig, Niemi and Silver in 1990, which has shown to be a more accurate measure for trust in government (Craig, Niemi, & Silver, 1990).

APCO Model

The APCO model is a macro model aiming to describe privacy and its relationship with other constructs. It considers privacy concerns as the central figure, with antecedents to the left of privacy concerns and outcomes and associated relationships to the right "antecedents → privacy concerns → outcomes" (Smith et al., 2011; Dinev, McConnell, & Smith, 2015). This study will primarily focus on the left-hand side of the APCO model, the antecedents of privacy concerns (Dinev et al., 2015; Xu, Dinev, Smith, & Hart, 2008). Figure 1 shows an overview of the APCO model.

Figure 1. APCO Model

Ultimately the goal of the APCO model is to create a macro model relating to privacy which finds applicability in a variety of disciplines and contexts. To achieve this goal the model is subject to a continuous process of improvement to generate an expanded set of antecedents and a full and complete set of outcomes (Smith et al., 2011).

In this research the APCO model antecedent's prior privacy experience, privacy awareness, demographic differences, computer anxiety and trust in government are used. While the first four of the above mentioned have been successfully validated in the privacy concerns context of e-commerce and social networking, the result may be different in the context of a CTA government solution in times of crisis because of the differences in personal and situational factors in this specific context. The latter antecedent "trust in government" is introduced by the researchers for the first time in the use of the APCO model for privacy concerns, since the app provider in this context is the government instead of a private company.

Research concerning trust and its relationship to privacy concerns have resulted in different understandings of the role of trust in this context. In previous studies trust is an antecedent to privacy concerns (Smith et al., 2011; Belanger, Hiller, & Smith, 2002) or outcome of privacy (Chellappa, 2008), but in others it has been shown to be a mediator between privacy concerns and observed behavior (Bansal et al., 2008). In this research trust will be recognized as an antecedent to privacy concerns.

Culture is also recognized as an antecedent to privacy concerns. As this research concerns the Netherlands and Germany this must be considered. The relationship between privacy concerns, government and culture is primarily dependent on the cultural elements of power distance and individualism (Thompson, 2019). On these two elements the Netherlands and Germany are similar (Hofstede, 2010), for this reason culture will be assumed to not influence the relationships in this research and will be excluded from analysis.

Information Boundary Theory

Information Boundary Theory (IBT) formed the theoretical basis for the APCO model (Xu et al., 2008; Dinev, et al., 2015). It addresses the social aspects of the disclosure of personal data. The theory states that each person has own defined boundaries. Depending on personal and situational factors, the perception of an individual varies as soon as an external organization requests personal data. Once this situation occurs, the individual evaluates the risks of disclosure in parallel with an assessment of the degree of control over the personal data disclosed. This process is described in the literature as risk-control

assessment (Klopper & Rubenstein, 1977).

While "boundary closure" in this concept describes the motivation of a refusal to release personal data, "boundary opening" describes the acceptance. This results from dynamic psychological processes, the use of the released information, the personal benefits from its release and the relationship between sender and receiver (Klopper & Rubenstein, 1977). IBT has enabled previous research on privacy concerns in different settings to identify different aspects of the emergence of privacy concerns (Smith et al., 2011).

Conceptual Model

The following findings in the research of privacy concerns have been derived by using IBT in researches from a different context. The authors of this research argue that selected previous findings about the antecedents of privacy concerns apply or contradict in the context of a governmental CTAs in times of COVID-19.

Evidence shows that people who have had personally negative experiences with data abuse have larger privacy concerns. At the same time, the findings show that media coverage has an impact on privacy concerns (Smith et al., 1996). However, this previous research only considers the general impact of privacy concerns. Changes brought about by digitalization and the context of COVID-19 could steer the results found at that time in a different direction. Accordingly, the researchers in this paper put forward the following hypothesis. The conceptual model can be found in figure 2.

H1: Negative prior privacy experiences increase privacy concerns about contact tracing apps.

When companies ask for a clear permission and thus enable consumers to control the data, privacy concerns decrease. At the same time privacy awareness is about the degree to which an individual is informed about an organization's use of their personal information. As a rule, the higher the level of knowledge about the use of the data, the greater the tendency of such persons to have privacy concerns (Malhotra, Sung, & Agarwal, 2004).

The authors believe that this behaves exactly the opposite of what was found in previous privacy research results in the case of the CTA, since citizens with a high level of privacy awareness should be familiar with the high technical privacy-related features of the CTA. Accordingly, the authors put forward the following hypothesis.

H2: Privacy awareness negatively influences privacy concerns about contact tracing apps.

Demographic factors can also significantly influence privacy concerns. Less educated people tend

to be less concerned about privacy in past studies (Culnan, 1999). There is, however, contradictory research. It shows that a higher level of education lowers the privacy concerns of internet users (Brown, 2007). Due to the high privacy-measurements of the CTA (CoronaMelder, 2020; Brecht, 2020), the researchers of this study assume different results, so that participants with a higher education have less privacy concerns due to the understanding of the guaranteed privacy. The following hypothesis emerges.

H3: Higher education levels decrease the privacy concerns about contact tracing apps.

Computer anxiety increases the privacy concerns of mobile app users. People that in general are more anxious about computers and technology also have higher privacy concerns towards the usage of contact tracing technology (Degirmenci, 2020).

H4: Computer anxiety increases the privacy concerns in the new context of contact tracing apps.

Citizens generally trust government organizations more than private companies when it comes to privacy (Cullen & Reilly, 2008). However, this distinction between private and governmental organizations is not evident when looking at previous mobile app research for privacy concerns. To determine this, the authors put forward the following hypothesis.

H5: Higher trust in the government decreases the privacy concerns about contact tracing apps.

According to prior research in the privacy context the intention of an individual to act in a certain way leads to an action (Pavlou, 2007). Therefore, the following hypothesis arises.

H6: Citizens' privacy concerns of tracing apps negatively influence the intention to accept the privacy of the contact tracing app.

Figure 2. Conceptual Model

RESEARCH DESIGN

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the study matter, a thorough literature review was conducted in the search engines Business Source Ultimate and Google Scholar. The selected papers were published in journals with impact factors higher than 3, or if published in a conference, the number of citations and the direct applicability to the topic was examined. Other sources include scholarly books for the research design. All sources were discussed among the researchers and peer reviewed for their quality and applicability to the topic.

This research follows a deductive approach, meaning that it starts with theories and ends with observations. Furthermore, the research base is quantitative with the aim to determine to what extent the discussed variables are related (correlation). Primary data has been gathered using a survey specifically designed for this research. The survey questions can be found in table 1 and table 2.

For the survey Qualtrics was used to collect the data from survey participants. Participants received a link to the online digital survey and could choose between the languages German, Dutch and English. All questions were closed ended, with the exception of the item “age”. The resulting data was finally exported to SPSS for in depth analysis.

Sampling process

The target population has been defined as “Dutch and German citizens during a pandemic” because this population recently introduced CTAs.

No concrete sample frame could be defined for this population. This forced nonprobability sampling for the sampling design (McCombes, 2020).

The used sampling design is convenience sampling because of the fast execution, which was required because of time constraints. Survey participants originate from the authors (social) networks. The digital social platforms Facebook, LinkedIn and WhatsApp were leveraged to increase reach within personal networks for participants.

Using the sample size table of Krejcie & Morgan (1970), and considering the target population is greater than 1,000,000, the minimum sample size for this research is 380, because this value remains relatively constant at this population size.

Measurement

Table 1 and table 2 include an overview of the variables in this study, its measurements and references. The table is adjusted in accordance with the APCO model. The variables are on a 7-point Likert and frequency scale (interval) with exception of the education level (ordinal).

The privacy concern is measured by its three constructs based on MUIPC. The average of these three constructs, which are all on a 7-point interval scale, is the value of the mediator.

Statistics

Hypothesis H3 will be tested with a one-way-ANOVA technique because the one factor education level (degree) contains more than two levels. This technique is used to compare means of more than two groups (Heijst, 2020).

Hypothesis H6 will be tested with a simple linear regression because privacy concern and acceptance are on a ratio scale. The objective of regression is to explain the variation of Y (Nieuwenhuis, 2009). In this research the variation of acceptance with privacy concern as independent variable will be explained using regression.

$$\gamma = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \varepsilon$$

Hypothesis H1, H2, H4 and H5 will be tested with multiple linear regression because all the relevant variables are on an interval scale. By introducing more variables into the model variation in Y may be further explained. (Nieuwenhuis, 2009).

$$\gamma = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Reliability

In this research a Cronbach's alpha score of at least 0.7 is considered acceptable. The corresponding scores to each variable can be found in the chapter results.

$$\frac{k}{k-1} \left(\frac{\text{sum of covariances}}{\text{sum of variances and covariances}} \right)$$

This survey uses off-the-shelf scales and adopted questionnaires which are used in previous research. Some of these questions were customized by this research to the context of COVID-19 and CTAs. The sources for the scales can be found in table 1 and table 2.

Validity

Before deploying the survey has been pre-tested. Pre-test participants all originated from the authors personal network and gave feedback on the duration time of the survey, similar-looking questions and translation errors.

In response to this, one independent variable was removed to shorten the survey. Regarding language and wording of the questionnaire, it is suggested that the language of the questionnaire should approximate the level of understanding of the respondents. If some questions are not understood or

interpreted differently, the consequences are biased results (Bougie & Sekaran, 2019). Efforts have been made to refine the survey after receiving pre-test feedback regarding the translation errors.

Participants were informed that the survey was anonymous. The survey introduction promised that no possible link to a person could be made from the data. Research reported lower social desirability for online surveys relative to pen-and-paper. Furthermore, anonymous participants scored significantly lower on measures of social desirability (Joinson, 1999).

Table 1. Operationalization of Antecedent Constructs

Construct	Measurement Items	Scale	Sources
Prior Privacy Experience	PPE1: How often have you personally been the victim of what you felt as an improper invasion of privacy?	7-point frequency scale (“never” to “always”)	(Xu et al., 2012)
	PPE2: How often have you personally experienced incidents whereby your personal information was used by an organisation without your authorization?		(Degirmenci, 2020)
	PPE3: How much have you heard or read during the last year about the use and potential misuse of computerized information about citizens?		(Smith et al., 1996)
Privacy Awareness	PA1: Organisations and governments seeking information from mobile apps should disclose the way the data are collected, processed and used.	7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”)	Malhotra et al., (2004)
	PA2: A good mobile app should have a clear and conspicuous privacy disclosure.		
	PA3: It is important to me that I am aware and knowledgeable about how my personal information will be used in a mobile app.		
Computer anxiety	CA1: Tracing apps are a real threat to privacy in this country.	7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”)	(Degirmenci, 2020)
	CA2: I am anxious and concerned about the pace of automation in the world.		(Stewart and Segars, 2002)
	CA3: I am sometimes frustrated by increasing automation in my home.		
Education	Less than high school, High School degree, College degree, Undergraduate degree, Graduate degree, Other.	Ordinal	(Degirmenci, 2020)
Trust	T1: How much of the time do you think you can trust the people who run your government to do what is right?	7-point frequency scale (“never” to “always”)	(Craig et al., 1990)
	T2: When government leaders make statements, how often do you think they are telling the truth?		
	T3: Do you think elected officials keep the promises they have made during the election?		
	T4: Do you think that most public officials can be trusted to do what is right without citizens having to constantly check on them?		

Table 2. Operationalization of Privacy Concern and Outcome Constructs

Construct /	Measurement Items	Scale	Sources
Perceived Surveillance	If I would download the tracing app...	7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”)	(Degirmenci, 2020) (Xu et al., 2012)
	PS1: I believe that my mobile device would be monitored at least part of the time.		
	PS2: I would be concerned that the tracing app is collecting too much information about me.		
Perceived Intrusion	If I would download the tracing app...	7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”)	(Degirmenci, 2020) (Xu et al., 2008)
	PI1: I feel that as a result, others would know about me more than I am comfortable with.		
	PI2: I believe that as a result, information about me that I consider private would be more readily available to others than I would want.		
Secondary Use of Personal Information	If I would download the tracing app...	7-point Likert scale (“strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”)	(Degirmenci, 2020) (Smith et al., 1996)
	SU1: I would be concerned that the tracing app may use my personal information for other purposes without notifying me or getting my authorization.		
	SU2: I would be concerned that the tracing app may use my information for other purposes.		
Acceptance of privacy-related Factors of CTAs	APF1: How do you perceive the privacy-related aspects of the corona tracing app in your country?	7-point Likert scale (“totally unacceptable” to “perfectly acceptable”)	Self-developed

RESULTS

There were 64 respondents that filled in the survey. Table 3 shows the Cronbach's Alpha for each variable that was used for the research design.

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Prior Privacy Experience	0.6223
Privacy awareness	0.7879
Computer anxiety	0.8054
Trust	0.8266
Perceived Surveillance	0.9402
Perceived Intrusion	0.9488
Secondary use of personal data	0.9606
Privacy Concerns	0.9465

A high Cronbach's Alpha is necessary to represent the reliability of a variable. There is a high Cronbach's Alpha if the outcome is 0.7 or higher, this means it is acceptable (Bland & Altman, 1997).

Table 4 shows the results of the multiple linear regression analysis for privacy concerns in the context of CTAs as the dependent variable, and as independent variables the antecedents discussed in the conceptual model. The table shows the constant and the coefficients of the slope for the four independent variables with accompanying significance levels.

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression

Slope/Intercept	Value	Significance
B0 (constant)	1.326	
B1: Privacy experience	0.260	0.171
B2: Privacy Awareness	0.108	0.541
B3: Computer Anxiety	0.604	0.000
B4: Government Trust	-0.344	0.055

Executing a one-way ANOVA in SPSS with degree (education level) as factor and privacy concern as dependent variable produced the following output: $F(4, 59) = 0.349, P = 0.844$.

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination

	R ²
Privacy Concerns	0.448

Finally, the authors analyze the relationship between the central construct privacy concerns and the acceptance of the privacy of the CTA (outcome) using a simple linear regression in table 6.

Table 6. Simple Linear Regression

Slope	Correlation coefficient	Significance
-0.703	-0.777	0.000

DISCUSSION

The only measure that is below the acceptable Cronbach's Alpha of 0.7 is Prior Privacy Experience (PPE). The rest of the variables are acceptable and do not have to change. It means that PPE has a weak internal consistency.

The results of the survey indicate that two of the five antecedents are significant with an alpha of 10%, which are computer anxiety and government trust. Government trust shows to have a negative effect of -0.344 on privacy concerns, confirming H5. Computer anxiety has the strongest positive effect on privacy concerns with a regression coefficient of 0.604. Confirming H4, that people who feel anxious about the level of technological advancements experience more privacy concerns towards CTAs. H3 cannot be accepted because of insignificant results.

The model's coefficient of determination is 0.448, meaning 44.8% of the variation in privacy concern can be explained by the model. It is likely that other variables are necessary in the analysis to provide better insight into the determinants of privacy concerns in relation to CTAs. Moreover, since three of the five proven antecedents of privacy concerns in the social media and e-commerce context are insignificant in the new context.

The negative correlation coefficient of -0.777 and an unstandardized slope of -0.703 of the relationship between the construct privacy concerns and the acceptance of the CTA privacy illustrate that higher privacy concerns of CTA can lead to a lower acceptance of the CTA privacy. Therefore, H6 is accepted.

The analysis revealed that both trust in government and computer anxiety have a significant effect on privacy concerns towards CTAs. Consequently, privacy experience and privacy awareness have an insignificant effect.

The following can be deduced as advice towards policy makers within government to improve the adoption of such apps towards the effective threshold of 60%. Current focus on privacy awareness through educating the public on the privacy protecting aspects of the apps are likely to be ineffective in increasing adoption. A strategy where building up trust in the morality, competence and truthfulness of government in terms of its approach to COVID-19 is advised. Accompanied by a strategy to decrease the public's anxiety towards technological developments such as CTAs. The operationalization of these strategies is outside of the scope of this research and should be further investigated. Figure 3 shows an overview of the results.

Figure 3. Results

CONCLUSION

Based on a modified APCO model this research investigated the antecedents that lead to increased privacy concerns for CTAs in times of a global pandemic. Existing literature has shown that certain antecedents affect the privacy concern. The context of a CTA in the era of COVID-19 in Germany and the Netherlands has shown that existing antecedents can have a different effect. Accordingly, this research highlights the importance of distinguishing between the different contexts in research on privacy concerns.

It can therefore be concluded that essential components of the APCO model have proven to be influencing factors of the privacy concerns and the intention to accept privacy of government CTAs. However, other established antecedents have shown to be insignificant. The contradictions to previous research and insignificance of existing antecedents show a need for further research in this specific context.

Limitations

The context of the COVID-19 crisis and the measures taken by governments change over time. Accordingly, this research can be considered as a temporal snapshot, limiting application over time. Similarly, the results of certain constructs can be influenced by other events of public concern. Privacy experience is one of such constructs that could be heavily influenced by public events. In addition, the dependent variable of intention to accept the privacy of the CTA was only examined with a single-item measure without testing its reliability due to the focus on the antecedents of the APCO model.

In this study convenience sampling was used because of time constraints, reducing generalizability of the results substantially. The survey was shared among the personal network of the authors, resulting in more than half of the survey participants being students, also reducing generalizability. Because of the small number of participants, there was no process in place for preparing or cleansing the data for abnormalities. After downloading the survey results from Qualtrics the data was analyzed. Moreover, the number of 380 participants has not been reached.

Through pre-testing the survey in different languages, the authors aimed to minimize possible mistakes from translation. However, no further research was done to examine and improve the international equivalence of the research.

Further research

More antecedents must be discovered and validated to apply the existing APCO model to applications provided by government. As the current understanding seems to be insufficient to explain privacy concerns. Further research should look into the antecedents which are related to the context of government with a focus on other countries than Germany and the Netherlands.

The use of other models could explain privacy concerns, especially with a focus on government trust. There are multiple models that explain privacy or privacy concerns. Further research could focus into the role of trust in government in privacy concerns.

REFERENCES

- Bansal, G., Zahedi, F., & Gefen, D. (2008). The Moderating Influence of Privacy Concern on the Efficacy of Privacy Assurance Mechanism for building Trust: A Multiple Context Investigation. *International Conference of Information Systems*, 29. Paris. Retrieved from <https://aisel.aisnet.org/icis2008/7/>
- Basu, S. (2020). Effective Contact Tracing for COVID-19 Using Mobile Phones: An Ethical Analysis of the Mandatory Use of the Aarogya Setu Application in India. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics*, 1-10. doi:10.1017/S0963180120000821
- Belanger, F., Hiller, S. J., & Smith, W. J. (2002). Trustworthiness in Electronic Commerce: The Role of Privacy, Security and Site Attributes. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 11, 245-270.
- Bland, J., & Altman, D. (1997). Statistics notes: Cronbach's alpha. *BMJ*, 314(7080), 572 - 572. doi:10.1136/bmj.314.7080.572
- Bock, K., Kühne, C., Mühlhoff, R., Ost, M., Pohle, J., & Rehak, R. (2020). Data Protection Impact Assessment for the Corona App. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 44 - 47. doi:10.2139/ssrn.3588172
- Bougie, R., & Sekaran, U. (2019). In R. Bougie, & U. Sekaran, *Research methods for business* (p. 147). Wiley.
- Brecht, C. T. (2020, Oktober). *SAP News Center*. Retrieved from <https://news.sap.com/germany/2020/10/pandemiebekämpfung-corona-warn-app/>
- Brown, I. Z. (2007, October). Examining the Influence of Demographic Factors on Internet Users' Information Privacy Concerns. *SAICSIT*, pp. 197-204.
- Centraal Bureau Statistiek. (2020, 10 27). *Bevolkingsteller*. Retrieved from CBS: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/visualisaties/bevolkingsteller>
- Chellappa, R. K. (2008). *Consumers Trust in Electronic Commerce Transactions: The Role of Perceived Privacy and Perceived Security*. Georgia: Emory University.
- CoronaMelder. (2020). *CoronaMelder Privacy Statement*. Retrieved from <https://www.coronamelder.nl/en/privacy-in-app.html>
- Craig, S., Niemi, R., & Silver, G. (1990). Political efficacy and trust: A report on the NES pilot study items. *Political Behavior*, 12(3), 289 - 314. doi:10.1007/bf00992337
- Cullen, R., & Reilly, P. (2008, October 11). Information Privacy and Trust in Government: A Citizen-Based Perspective from New Zealand. *Journal of Information Technology*, pp. 61 - 80.
- Culnan, M. J. (1999). Consumer Awareness of Name Removal Procedures: Implication for Direct Marketing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing* (9), pp. 10 - 19.
- Degirmenci, K. (2020). Mobile users' information privacy concerns and the role of app permission requests. *International Journal of Information Management* 50 (2020) , pp. 261–272.
- Deutscher Ärzteverlag GmbH. (2020, Juli). *Ärzteblatt*. Retrieved from <https://www.aerzteblatt.de/nachrichten/114871/7-5-Millionen-Euro-fuer-Corona-Warn-App-Werbung>
- Dinev, T., & Hart, P. (2006). An Extended Privacy Calculus Model for E-Commerce Transactions. *Information Systems Research*, 17(1), 61 - 80. doi:10.1287/isre.1060.0080
- Dinev, T., McConnell, A. R., & Smith, H. J. (2015). Informing privacy research through information systems, psychology and behavioural economics: Thinking outside the APCO box. *Information Systems Research*, 26(4), 639-655.
- Eastlick, M., Lotz, S., & Warrington, P. (2006). Understanding online B-to-C relationships: An integrated model of privacy concerns, trust, and commitment. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(8), 877 - 886. doi:10.1016/j.jbusres.2006.02.006
- European Union. (2020, October 19). *European Commission*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/QANDA_20_1905
- Heijst, L. v. (2020, 11 26). *ANOVA uitvoeren en interpreteren*. Opgehaald van Scribbr: <https://www.scribbr.nl/statistiek/anova/>
- Hinch, R. (2020). *Effective configurations of a digital contact tracing app: A report to NHSX*. Retrieved from Github: https://github.com/BDI-pathogens/covid-19_instant_tracing/blob/master/Report
- Hofstede, G. J. (2010). *Cultures and organizations: Software of the mind. Revised and Expanded 3rd Edition*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Joinson, A. (1999). Social desirability, anonymity, and Internet-based questionnaires. *Behavior Research Methods, Instruments, & Computers*, 433.
- Joseph, R. (2013). A structured analysis of e-government studies: Trends and opportunities. *Government Information Quarterly*, 435-440.
- Keith, M. J., Babb, S. J., Lowrey, B. P., Furner, C. p., & Abdullat, A. (2015). The role of mobile-computing self-efficacy in consumer information disclosure. *Information Systems Journal*, 637-667.
- Klopfer, P. H., & Rubenstein, D. I. (1977). The Concept Privacy and its Biological Basis. *Journal of Social Issues* (33:3), pp. 52 - 65.
- Krejcie, R., & Morgan, D. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 1.
- Malhotra, N. K., Sung, K. S., & Agarwal, J. (2004, December). Internet Users' Information Privacy Concerns (IUIPC): The Construct, the Scale, and a Causal Model. *Information Systems Research Vol. 15, No. 4*, pp. 336 - 355.
- McCombes, S. (2020, November 13). *Non-probability sampling methods*. Retrieved from Scribbr: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/sampling-methods/#non-probability-sampling>
- Medicus, M. (2020, November). *Corona-Warn-App: Downloads überschreiten 22-Millionen-Marke*. Retrieved from Connect: <https://www.connect.de/news/corona-warn-app-download-zahlen-3200860.html>
- Nieuwenhuis, G. (2009). *Statistical Methods for Business and Economics*. McGraw Hill education.
- Pavlou, P. A. (2007). Understanding and mitigating uncertainty in online exchange relationships: A principal-agent perspective. *MIS Quarterly*, 31(1), pp. 105-136.
- Pee, L. G. (2011). ATTENUATING PERCEIVED PRIVACY RISK. *European Conference on Information Systems*, (p. 238).
- Rijksoverheid. (2020). *Coronavirus: televisiespots, animatievideo's en radiospots*. Retrieved from <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/coronavirus-covid-19/coronavirus-beeld-en-video/tv-spots-radiospots-en-animatievideos>
- Rijksoverheid. (2020). *Voorkom verspreiding, download CoronaMelder*. Retrieved from Coronamelder: <https://coronamelder.nl/>
- Rijksoverheid. (2020). *Vraag en antwoord*. Retrieved from CoronaMelder: <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/coronavirus-app/vraag-en-antwoord/hoe-werkt-de-corona-app>
- Robert-Koch-Institut. (2020). *Open-Source Project Corona-Warn-App*. Retrieved from coronawarn: <https://www.coronawarn.app/en/>
- Roorda. (2020, 10 13). *CoronaMelder App campagne start Dinsdag*. Retrieved from Emerce: <https://www.emerce.nl/wire/coronamelder-app-campagne-start-dinsdag>
- Saurav, B. (2020). Effective Contact Tracing for COVID-19 Using Mobile Phones: An Ethical Analysis of the Mandatory Use of the Aarogya Setu Application in India. *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics*, 1-10. doi:10.1017/S0963180120000821
- Sheehan, K., & Hoy, M. (2000). Dimensions of Privacy Concern among Online Consumers. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 19(1), 62 - 73. doi:10.1509/jppm.19.1.62.16949
- Smith, H. J., Milberg, S. J., & Burke, S. J. (1996, June). Information Privacy: Measuring Individuals' Concerns About Organizational Practices. *MIS Quarterly*, pp. 167 - 196.
- Smith, H., Dinev, T., & Xu Heng. (2011, 12 01). Information Privacy Research: An Interdisciplinary Review. *MIS Quarterly*, 35, 989 - 1015. doi:10.2307/41409970
- Thompson, N. M. (2019, August). Cultural factors and the role of privacy concerns in acceptance of government surveillance. *Jasist Wiley*, pp. 1129 - 1142. Retrieved from DOI: 10.1002/asi.24372
- Trang, S., Trenz, M., Weiger, W. H., & Cheung, M. T. (2020, Juli 27). One app to trace them all? Examining app specifications for mass acceptance of contact-tracing apps. *European Journal of Information Systems 2020, VOL. 29, NO. 4*, pp. 415-428.
- Walrave, M., Waeterloos, c., & Ponnet, K. (2020). Adoption of a Contact Tracing App for

Containing COVID-19: A Health Belief Model Approach. *JMIR Public Health and Surveillance*, 6(3), e20572.
doi:10.2196/20572

WHO. (2020). *Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>

Xu, H., Dinev, T., Smith, J. H., & Hart, P. (2008). Examining the Formation of Individual's Privacy Concerns: Toward an Integrative View. *ICIS*, (p. 6).

Xu, H., Gupta, S., Rossen, M. B., & Carroll, J. M. (2012). Measuring Mobile Users' Concerns for Information Privacy. *International Conference on Information Systems*.